

The Fetal
Medicine Foundation

18th World Congress In Fetal Medicine

Alicante 2019

18th World Congress in Fetal Medicine

Tuesday 25th June 2019: Joint session with Eurofoetus

- 09:10 - 10:00 Achilles tendon of fetal surgery
- 10:00 - 10:35 Gastroschisis: novel indication for fetal surgery
- 10:35 - 13:00 Special lectures
- 14:30 - 19:30 Twins: counselling of prospective parents
- 21:00 - 24:00 Welcome reception

Wednesday 26th June 2019: Joint session with Eurofoetus

- 09:00 - 10:20 Congenital diaphragmatic hernia
- 10:20 - 16:00 Open spina bifida
- 16:00 - 16:30 New approaches to fetal therapy
- 17:15 - 19:30 Preterm birth

Thursday 27th June 2019

- 09:00 - 09:40 Congenital infection
- 09:40 - 10:30 Special topics
- 10:30 - 13:00 Fetal growth restriction
- 14:30 - 19:00 Preeclampsia
- 19:00 - 19:15 New insights into obstetric cholestasis and GDM

Friday 28th June 2019

- 09:00 - 13:00 Fetal echocardiography
- 14:30 - 17:40 Screening and diagnosis of aneuploidies
- 17:40 - 19:30 Fetal ultrasound meets genetics

Saturday 29th June 2019

- 09:00 - 09:16 First trimester anomaly scan
- 09:16 - 09:50 Special lectures
- 09:50 - 10:40 Labor and birth
- 10:40 - 11:00 Obesity and diabetes
- 11:30 - 13:00 Neurosonography

Tuesday 25th June 2019: Joint session with Eurofoetus

08:00 - 09:00 Registration

09:00 - 09:10 **Welcome**

Kypros Nicolaides (UK)

09:10 - 10:00 **Achilles tendon of fetal surgery**

Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Michael Belfort (USA)

09:10 - 09:22 **Effect of hydration status on fetal membrane frailty**

09:22 - 09:29 **Chorioamniotic membrane separation after spina bifida repair**

09:29 - 09:36 **A sealing system for fetoscopic defects**

09:36 - 09:43 **Nature and occurrence of fetal surgery complications**

09:43 - 09:50 **Outcome of subsequent pregnancies after open spina bifida repair**

09:50 - 10:00 **Panel discussion**

Edoardo Mazza (Switzerland)

Romain Cormoene (USA)

Elisenda Eibarich (Spain)

Adalino Sacco (UK)

Julie Moldenhauer (USA)

10:00 - 10:35 **Gastroschisis: novel indication for fetal surgery**

Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Alexandra Benachi (France)

10:00 - 10:12 **Prenatal findings and natural history**

10:12 - 10:19 **Experimental in utero closure**

10:19 - 10:30 **Strategy for a clinical in utero surgery**

10:30 - 10:35 **Panel discussion**

Paolo De Coppi (UK)

Luc Joyeux (Belgium)

Sundeep Keswani (USA)

10:35 - 13:00 **Special lectures**

Discussants: Tessa Homfray (UK), Magdalena Sanz (USA)

10:35 - 10:45 **Fetal brain development in CDH - MRI study**

10:45 - 11:00 **Agensis of the corpus callosum**

Michael Aertsen (Belgium)

Daniela Prayer (Austria)

11:00 - 11:30 **Coffee break**

11:30 - 11:45 **Exome sequencing analysis in fetal defects**

11:45 - 12:00 **3D atlas of human embryology**

12:00 - 12:15 **How a dead duck changed my life**

12:15 - 12:30 **Imaging genetics of the human face**

12:30 - 12:45 **Intrauterine determinants of adult disease**

12:45 - 13:00 **Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders**

Mark Kilby (UK)

Bernadette de Bakker (Netherlands)

Kees Moeliker (Netherlands)

Peter Claes (Belgium)

Kirsten Poore (UK)

David Germanaud (France)

13:00 - 14:30 **Lunch break**

14:30 - 19:30 **Twins: counselling of prospective parents**

Chairs: Yves Ville (France), Liesbeth Lewi (Belgium)

14:30 - 14:37 **Embryo reduction in DC twins and TC triplets**

14:37 - 14:44 **Embryo reduction in DC twins and risk of PE**

14:44 - 14:51 **Embryo reduction in DC triplets - radiofrequency ablation**

14:51 - 14:58 **3rd trimester selective reduction in MC twins**

14:58 - 15:10 **Discordant anomalies in DC and MC twins**

15:10 - 15:20 **Panel discussion**

15:20 - 15:32 **Death of one fetus in DC and MC twins**

15:32 - 15:42 **Emotional consequences of single death in twins**

15:42 - 15:52 **Panel discussion**

15:52 - 16:04 **Monoamniotic twins**

16:04 - 16:16 **Conjoined twins**

16:16 - 16:23 **Panel discussion**

16:23 - 16:30 **Outcome of spontaneous vs ART MC twins**

Shlomo Lipitz (Israel)

Veronica Accurti (Italy)

Vivian Dimitriadi (UK)

Sanne Deneckere (Belgium)

Liesbeth Lewi (Belgium)

Mark Kilby (UK)

Elena Carreras (Spain)

Tim Van Mieghem (Canada)

Paolo De Coppi (UK)

Alicia Martinez-Varea (Spain)

16:30 - 17:10 **Coffee break**

17:10 - 17:17 **Selective FGR: evolution in Doppler patterns**

17:17 - 17:24 **Selective FGR type 2: endoscopic laser**

17:24 - 17:31 **TTTS +/- sFGR: short and long-term outcomes**

17:31 - 17:40 **Panel discussion**

17:40 - 17:52 **TTTS stages 3 and 4**

17:52 - 18:04 **TTTS stages 1 and 2**

18:04 - 18:11 **TTTS < 18 w**

18:11 - 18:18 **Solomon dichorionization: the primary treatment for all TTTS patients**

18:18 - 18:25 **Patient-specific planning platform for TTTS surgery**

18:25 - 18:40 **Panel discussion**

18:40 - 18:50 **TTTS perioperative hemodynamics and neurodevelopment**

18:50 - 19:00 **TAPS: diagnostic criteria and outcome**

19:00 - 19:07 **TAPS: international registry of > 300 cases**

19:07 - 19:13 **TAPS: trial on marlageant**

19:13 - 19:20 **Normal fetal Doppler in MC twins vs. singletons**

19:20 - 19:30 **Panel discussion**

Luyao Li (China)

Ramona Chmait (USA)

Sophie Groenen (Netherlands)

Kurt Hecher (Germany)

Yves Ville (France)

Asma Khali (UK)

Mara Rosner (USA)

Elisenda Eibarich (Spain)

Manon Gijtenbeek (Netherlands)

Enrico Oppioire (Netherlands)

Lisanne Tollenaar (Netherlands)

Lisanne Tollenaar (Netherlands)

Daniela Salsati (Italy)

Wednesday 26th June 2019: Joint session with Eurofoetus

09:00 - 10:20	Congenital diaphragmatic hernia Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Alexandra Benachi (France)	David Basurto (Mexico / Belgium) Jimmy Espinoza (USA) Hanane Bouchghoul (France) Lennart Van der Veeken (Belgium) David Basurto (Mexico / Belgium) Vivien Dutemeyer (Belgium)
09:00 - 09:07	Prediction of pulmonary hypertension	
09:07 - 09:14	Pulmonary hypertension in FETO patients	
09:14 - 09:21	Does the gestational age at delivery matter?	
09:21 - 09:28	Fetal brain development in CDH - US study	
09:28 - 09:35	Smart tracheal occlusion	
09:35 - 09:42	MRI assessment of lung volumes	
09:42 - 09:50	Panel discussion	
09:50 - 10:20	Severe CDH: debate on FETO outside the TOTAL trial Discussants: Kurt Hecher (Germany), Jacques Jani (Belgium)	Yves Ville vs. Jan Deprest
10:20 - 16:00	Open spina bifida Discussants: Jan Deprest (Belgium), Magdalena Sanz (USA)	
10:20 - 10:35	1st trimester diagnosis of spina bifida: 10 years later	
10:35 - 10:45	Spina bifida: ultrasound assessment	
10:45 - 10:52	Spina bifida: functional deterioration	
10:52 - 11:00	Panel discussion	Rabih Chaoui (Germany) Elena Carreras (Spain) Francesca Russo (Belgium)
11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break		
11:30 - 11:37	Spina bifida: evolution in ventriculomegaly	
11:37 - 11:44	Spina bifida: other brain anomalies	
11:44 - 11:51	Spina bifida: genetic anomalies	
11:51 - 12:00	Spina bifida: technique of postnatal repair Debate: indications, neurosurgical technique, membranes and prematurity	Tim Van Mieghem (Canada) Lucas Trigo (Spain / Brazil) Selima Ben Miled (France) William Whitehead (USA)
12:00 - 12:05	Introduction	
12:05 - 12:15	- Hysterotomy	
12:15 - 12:25	- Mini-hysterotomy	
12:25 - 12:35	- Fetoscopy via laparotomy	
12:35 - 12:45	- Fetoscopy percutaneous	
12:45 - 13:00	Panel discussion	Jan Deprest (Belgium) Julie Moldenhauer (USA) Fabio Peralta (Brazil) Michael Belfort (USA) Denise Lapa (Brazil)
13:00 - 14:30 Lunch break		
Debate: dissemination of spina bifida repair		
14:30 - 14:45	Fetal surgery registry: hysterotomy	
14:45 - 15:00	Fetal surgery registry: fetoscopy	Julie Moldenhauer (USA) Magdalena Sanz (USA) Luc Joyeux (Belgium) Martin Meuli (Switzerland)
15:00 - 15:10	Fetal surgery: learning curve	
15:10 - 15:20	Open repair: maternal and fetal complications	
15:20 - 15:30	Panel discussion	
15:30 - 15:37	Fetal surgery: effect on fetal Doppler	
15:37 - 15:44	Fetal surgery: effect on motor function	
15:44 - 15:53	Fetal surgery: effect on posterior fossa and brain stem	
15:53 - 16:00	Panel discussion	Rogelio Cruz Martinez (Mexico) Romain Corroenne (USA) Thomas Deprest (Belgium)
16:00 - 16:30	New approaches to fetal therapy Discussants: Dick Oepkes (Netherlands), Michael Belfort (USA)	
16:00 - 16:10	Neck tumors: fetal tracheoscopy and intubation	
16:10 - 16:20	Rh disease: treatment with M281	
16:20 - 16:30	Thulium laser in fetal medicine	Rogelio Cruz Martinez (Mexico) Dick Oepkes (Netherlands) Michael Belfort (USA)
16:30 - 17:15 Coffee break		
17:15 - 19:30	Preterm birth Discussants: Roberto Romero (USA), Gerry Visser (Netherlands)	
17:15 - 17:30	Preterm birth: survival and long term outcome	
17:30 - 17:40	Need for steroids at 34-37 weeks	
17:40 - 17:50	Panel discussion	Enrico Lopriore (Netherlands) Gerry Visser (Netherlands)
17:50 - 18:00	Prediction of preterm birth and intraamniotic infection	
18:00 - 18:20	Treatment of intraamniotic infection and intraamniotic inflammation	
18:20 - 18:30	Panel discussion	Teresa Cobo (Spain) Roberto Romero (USA)
18:30 - 18:37	Prediction in twins: single vs serial measurements of cervical length	
18:37 - 18:44	Cervical consistency in singletons and twins	
18:44 - 18:51	Prediction of imminent birth: cervical sliding sign	
18:51 - 18:58	Cervical length screening depends on population characteristics	
18:58 - 19:05	Preterm clinic: prediction and prevention of preterm birth	
19:05 - 19:20	New ideas about preterm labor	
19:20 - 19:30	Panel discussion	Cesar Mellor (Argentina) Liona Poon (China) Nicola Volpe (Italy) Gerry Visser (Netherlands) Meekai To (UK) Roberto Romero (USA)

Thursday 27th June 2019

09:00 - 09:40	Congenital infection Discussant: Yves Ville (France)	
09:00 - 09:06	HIV treated by antiretrovirals: infant cardiac remodelling	Laura Garcia Otero (Spain)
09:06 - 09:12	CMV infection: knowledge by healthcare providers	Anna Gonca (Spain)
09:12 - 09:18	CMV infection <14 w: standardized assessment	Valentine Faure-Bardon (France)
09:18 - 09:30	CMV infection: new concepts	Yves Ville (France)
09:30 - 09:40	Questions on management	Asma Khalil (UK)
09:40 - 10:30	Special topics Discussants: Jon Hyett (Australia), Yves Ville (France)	
09:40 - 09:55	Cesarean section: long term consequences for the child	Zarko Alfirevic (UK)
09:55 - 10:07	Intrauterine interventions in congenital heart disease	Wolfgang Arzt (Austria)
10:07 - 10:15	Meta-analysis on in utero stem cell transplantation	Rachel Sagar (UK)
10:15 - 10:30	Urogenital defects: postnatal management	Marie-Klaire Farrugia (UK)
10:30 - 13:00	Fetal growth restriction Discussants: Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Francesc Figueras (Spain)	
10:30 - 10:40	Identification of different phenotypes of FGR	Fatima Crispi (Spain)
10:40 - 10:50	Competing risks model for prediction of SGA	Ioannis Papastefanou (Greece)
10:50 - 11:00	Fetal growth in IVF/ICSI pregnancies	Paolo Cavoretto (Italy)
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break	
11:30 - 11:40	Cardiac dysfunction and hypoxia in SGA fetuses	Fatima Crispi (Spain)
11:40 - 11:47	Adverse perinatal outcome at term: Uta-PI, CPR and growth	Gerard Albaiges (Spain)
11:47 - 11:53	Adverse perinatal outcome at term: biomarkers of impaired placentation	Hila De Castro (UK)
11:53 - 12:03	IPD Meta-analysis of CPR in prediction of adverse perinatal outcome	Ben Mol (Netherlands)
12:03 - 12:10	Cortical development in PE and FGR	Francesca Crovetto (Spain)
12:10 - 12:25	Early FGR: management	Christoph Lees (UK)
12:25 - 12:40	Late FGR: management	Francesc Figueras (Spain)
12:40 - 12:50	3rd trimester prediction of SGA neonates	Kypros Nicolaides (UK)
12:50 - 13:00	Panel discussion	
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch break	
14:30 - 19:00	Preeclampsia Discussants: Liona Poon, Stefan Verlohren, Kypros Nicolaides	
14:30 - 14:45	Are early PE and early sPTB the same disease?	Carl Weiner (USA)
14:45 - 14:57	Proteomics, metabolomics and lipidomics in early PE	Lina Youssef (Spain)
14:57 - 15:04	Relation of uterine artery and ophthalmic artery Doppler in PE	Markus Gonsler (Germany)
15:04 - 15:11	Maternal congenital heart disease and PE	Raigam Martinez-Portiella (Spain)
15:11 - 15:20	Panel discussion	
15:20 - 15:32	FIGO guidelines for 1st trimester prediction and prevention	Liona Poon (China)
15:32 - 15:44	Appropriate implementation of screening	David Wright (UK)
15:44 - 15:54	Implementation of screening in Asia	Liona Poon (China)
15:54 - 16:04	Implementation of screening in Spain	Mar Gil (Spain)
16:04 - 16:11	Implications of new definitions of PE	Naila Khan (UK)
16:11 - 16:18	Low-dose aspirin <11 w: meta-analysis	Piya Chaemsaihong (China)
16:18 - 16:30	Panel discussion	
16:30 - 17:15	Coffee break	
17:15 - 17:25	2 nd and 3 rd trimester prediction and management	Stefan Verlohren (Germany)
17:25 - 17:32	Screening in the 2nd trimester	Magdalena Litwinska (UK)
17:32 - 17:39	Screening in the 3rd trimester	Anca Ciobanu (UK)
17:39 - 17:46	sFlt1/PlGF value >655: maternal and perinatal outcomes	Cecilia Villalain (Spain)
17:46 - 17:56	sFLT and PLGF to predict PE in women with hypertension	Nikos Kameitais (UK)
17:56 - 18:06	Imminent PE: Congo red	Howard Cuckle (Israel)
18:06 - 18:15	Panel discussion	
18:15 - 18:25	RCT: Enoxaparin for prevention of PE and FGR	Elisa Llorca (Spain)
18:25 - 18:35	RCT: High dose folic acid for prevention of PE	Mark Walker (Canada)
18:35 - 18:45	RCT: Prediction and prevention in twins	Zsolt Benko (UK)
18:45 - 19:00	Panel discussion	
19:00 - 19:30	New insights into obstetric cholestasis and GDM	Catherine Williamson (UK)

Friday 28th June 2019

- 09:00 - 13:00 Fetal echocardiography**
Discussants: John Simpson (UK), Rabih Chaoui (Germany)
- 09:00 - 09:12 Core concepts in fetal cardiac function**
- 09:12 - 09:24 2D strain, twist and torsion -- what is it all about?**
- 09:24 - 09:36 Functional changes from prenatal to postnatal life**
- 09:36 - 09:46 2D strain in coarctation of the aorta**
- 09:46 - 09:56 What about the third dimension?**
- 09:56 - 10:06 Fetal cardiac function in disease states**
- 10:06 - 10:16 1st trimester vasculature imaging**
- 10:16 - 10:30 Venous anomalies**
- 10:30 - 10:45 What's new in STIC imaging?**
- 10:45 - 11:00 Impact of computerisation / artificial intelligence**

- Fatima Crispi (Spain)
John Simpson (UK)
Olga Patey (UK)
Trisha Vigneswaran (UK)
Christian Ensenberger (Germany)
Marietta Charakida (UK)
Vita Zidere (UK)
Rabih Chaoui (Germany)
Balu Vaidyanathan (India)
David Lloyd (UK)

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee break

- 11:30 - 12:10 Presentation of cases**
- 12:10 - 12:17 Fetal cardiac remodeling and dysfunction in PE and FGR**
- 12:17 - 12:24 Sirolimus for fetal cardiac rhabdomyoma**
- 12:24 - 12:31 Longitudinal changes in congenital atrioventricular block**
- 12:31 - 12:38 Sonopathological correlation of 1st trimester cardiac defects**
- 12:38 - 12:45 Right ventricular outflow tract anomalies in MC twins**
- 12:45 - 12:52 2-year follow up of prenatally diagnosed univentricular heart**
- 12:52 - 13:00 Early diagnosis of TOF and malalignment VSD**

- Lina Youssef (Spain)
Tim Van Mieghem (Canada)
Monica Cruz-Lemini (Mexico)
Sudarshan Suresh (India)
Stefano Faiola (Italy)
Silvia Andres (Argentina)
Valentina De Robertis (Italy)

13:00 - 14:30 Lunch break

- 14:30 - 17:40 Screening and diagnosis of aneuploidies**
Discussants: Francesca Grati, Thomas Musci, Kypros Nicolaides
- 14:30 - 14:42 Comprehensive paradigm for prenatal diagnosis**
- 14:42 - 14:49 New insights into risk of miscarriage after CVS**
- 14:49 - 14:56 cfDNA for T21, T18, T13: performance of screening in singletons and twins**
- 14:56 - 15:03 cfDNA for T21 and T18: contingent screening in singletons**
- 15:03 - 15:10 Evolution in prenatal detection of chromosomal aberrations**
- 15:10 - 15:27 National programme for clinical implementation of screening**
- 15:27 - 15:37 Effectiveness of prenatal testing for T21**
- 15:37 - 15:44 cfDNA test failure in autoimmune diseases**
- 15:44 - 15:51 cfDNA test in vanishing twin**
- 15:51 - 15:58 cfDNA test to determine zygosity in twins**
- 15:58 - 16:05 cfDNA for DiGeorge: performance of screening**
- 16:05 - 16:17 Universal cfDNA testing by genome wide approach**
- 16:17 - 16:27 Arguments against genome wide cfDNA testing**

- Antoni Borrell (Spain)
Francisca Molina (Spain)
Mar Gil (Spain)
Shelley Dougan (Canada)
Pavel Calda (Czechia)
Ann Tabor (Denmark)
Eugene Pergament (USA)
Alexandra Benachi (France)
Jacques Jani (Belgium)
Peter Benn (USA)
Oliver Kagan (Germany)
Mireille Bekker (Netherlands)
Francesca Grati (Italy)

16:30 - 17:15 Coffee break

- 17:15 - 17:22 cfDNA test in early pregnancy losses**
- 17:22 - 17:32 Fetal cells in maternal blood**
- 17:32 - 17:40 Panel discussion**

- Antoni Borrell (Spain)
Jiri Sonek (USA)

- 17:40 - 19:30 Fetal ultrasound meets genetics**
Presenters: Tessa Homfray (UK), Katia Billardo (Netherlands)
Rabih Chaoui (Germany), Oliver Kagan (Germany), Elena Greco (UK)

Saturday 29th June 2019

09:00 - 09:16	First trimester anomaly scan Discussants: Katia Billardo (Netherlands), Jon Hyett (Australia)	
09:00 - 09:06	Methodological standardization of the 11-13 week scan	Nicola Volpe (Italy)
09:06 - 09:16	Performance of routine screening	Argyro Syngelaki (UK)
09:16 - 09:50	Special lectures Discussants: Katia Billardo (Netherlands), Jon Hyett (Australia)	
09:16 - 09:28	Birth asphyxia and cerebral palsy	Gerry Visser (Netherlands)
09:28 - 09:38	Maternal mortality across Europe	Anca Panaitescu (Romania)
09:38 - 09:50	Management of morbidly adherent placenta	Mohamed Montaz (Egypt)
09:50 - 10:40	Labor and birth Discussants: Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Jon Hyett (Australia)	
09:50 - 10:00	Macrosomia: adverse perinatal outcome	Ranjit Akolekar (UK)
10:00 - 10:07	Machine learning model for prediction of shoulder dystocia	Abraham Tsur (USA)
10:07 - 10:14	Levator ani co-activation in the active second stage of labor	Rasha Kamel (Egypt)
10:14 - 10:21	Cervical shear wave elastography: prediction of outcome in labor induction	Tak Yeung Leung (China)
10:21 - 10:28	Prediction of placenta previa at the 20 week scan	Charlotte Jansen (Netherlands)
10:28 - 10:40	Re-engineering the interpretation of fetal monitoring	Mark Evans (USA)
10:40 - 11:00	Obesity and diabetes Discussants: Gerry Visser (Netherlands), Jon Hyett (Australia)	
10:40 - 10:47	The impact of maternal obesity on gestation-specific risk of stillbirth	Naila Ramji (Canada)
10:47 - 10:54	Does bariatric surgery change pregnancy outcome?	Alexandra Matias (Portugal)
10:54 - 11:01	Prediction of the need for insulin treatment in gestational diabetes mellitus	Makarios Eleftheriades (Greece)
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break	
11:30 - 13:00	Neurosonography Discussants: Magdalena Sanz (USA), Elisenda Eixarch (Spain)	
11:30 - 11:37	Isolated non-severe ventriculomegaly: neurodevelopment	Nadine Hahner (Spain)
11:37 - 11:44	Routine assessment of proximal hemisphere	Lorena Hormazabal (Chile)
11:44 - 11:56	Consequences of short corpus callosum	Eldad Katorza (Israel)
11:56 - 12:03	Corpus callosum in congenital heart defects	Miriam Pérez-Cruz (Spain)
12:03 - 12:15	Panel discussion	
12:15 - 12:35	Sonographic visualization of the optic chiasm	Guillermo Azumendi (Spain)
12:35 - 13:00	Presentation of diagnostic challenges	Ritsuko Pooh (Japan)
13:00 - 14:30	Lunch break	

Prenatally detected case of CCAM type 1 associated with deficiency of alpha 1 antitrypsin

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Objective

Reported incidence of congenital cystic adenomatoid malformation (CCAM) ranges from 1: 11.000 to 1: 35.000 live births. CCAM of the lung is a rare bronchopulmonary anomaly, and may be frequently associated with cardiac and renal anomalies. CCAM may rarely be associated with hydrops and chromosome abnormalities. According to embryologic level of origin and the histological features there CCAM is classified with five main types. Possible outcome is resolution of the lesion either antenatal or postnatal. After birth, symptoms are ranging from asymptomatic to severe and progressive respiratory distress.

Methods

This is a case report.

Results

A 28-year-old woman and 31-year-old man were referred to geneticist because of prenatally detected fetal CCAM type 1 in 23rd week of gestation. It was first pregnancy. During pregnancy mother received metformin because of insulin resistance. Delivery was in GA 40⁺⁴; BW 3350g, BL 48 cm, HC 34cm, AS 9/9. After birth, newborn was monitored but did not have any respiratory difficulties. Diagnosis of CCAM was confirmed with CT scan. No other congenital malformation was found. Laboratory analyses showed lower level of alpha 1 antitrypsin: 1.22. ..1.04. .. .0.94 g/L (r. v. 1.24-3.48) caused by alpha-1 antitrypsin S mutation in heterozygote state. Patient was followed for respiratory function. Surgical treatment was considered and postponed.

Conclusion

Routine prenatal ultrasonography has increased the frequency of prenatal diagnosis of congenital malformations of the lung including CCAM, which allows proper planning per partum and neonatal management. In most cases, prognosis is good. Nevertheless, because CCAM could contain tissue from different pulmonary origins that has malignant potential, surgical treatment is recommended. We consider that occurrence of CCAM and AAT deficiency in this case was incidental.